

Induced polarization effects in fixed-wing airborne EM: the TEMPEST™ system—Part B, field data inversion from regional targeting to deposit-scale characterization

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SUMMARY

This paper is the second part of a series examining the effects of ground polarization in airborne electromagnetic (AEM) data collected with fixed-wing platforms. Induced polarization (IP) effects can be detected using airborne electromagnetic methods; however, most geophysical studies have focused on helicopter-borne systems whose sensitivity to subsurface polarizable features is well established. In contrast, the potential of fixed-wing AEM systems for IP detection remains largely unexplored, and their effects have not yet been modelled. Building on Part A of this series, which examined the sensitivity of TEMPEST™ system to ground chargeability with numerical analysis and dataspace inspection, we extend the study using field survey data to model subsurface IP effects in inversion. This study is defined at three different exploration scales: deposit scale, survey-line and regional scale. The first experiment focuses on a comparative modelling analysis between the TEMPEST™ and SkyTEM³¹²FAST helicopter-borne system along two overlapping survey lines. The results show highly comparable chargeability and resistivity distributions, with consistent outcomes across the TEMPEST™ measured components (X and Z) and with geological interpretation of the area. These findings demonstrate that fixed-wing AEM can effectively resolve IP anomalies with resolution and depth penetration similar to helicopter-borne systems, despite differences in acquisition geometry and system design. Then, to assess regional-scale applicability, the entire Musgrave Province in South Australia was inverted incorporating IP effects and comparing the results with the non-IP modelling of the area. The IP modelling show a systematically reduction of inversion misfit, when compared with non-AIP modelling with differences between the resistivity models higher than 100 per cent. To conclude, the ground truthing of regional modelling has been carried over the well-characterized Nemo-Babel mineralization. This confirmed that TEMPEST™ derived chargeability anomalies align closely with known mineralized zones, validating both spatial accuracy and correspondence with mineralization of the modelled resistivity and chargeability. Overall, this study demonstrates that fixed-wing AEM platforms, such as TEMPEST™, can detect and quantify ground chargeability from regional to deposit scale, providing a valuable tool to target exploration and to characterize mineralized bodies.

Key words: Electrical properties; Australia; Electromagnetic theory; Induced polarization.

INTRODUCTION

Induced polarization (IP) is a geophysical phenomenon in which subsurface materials exhibit chargeable or capacitive behaviour when subjected to an electrical current, producing a voltage response commonly linked to disseminated sulphides, clays and graphite (J.S. Sumner 1976; W.H. Pelton *et al.* 1978). Traditionally, IP has been measured using galvanic methods with direct current or low-frequency signals, but it can also be detected inductively when time-varying electromagnetic (EM) fields are applied (e.g. M. Flis 1987; R.S. Smith & J. Klein 1996). This phenomenon, termed inductive induced polarization, is increasingly relevant in airborne electromagnetic (AEM) surveys, where polarizable materials distort transient EM decay curves. These distortions complicate resistivity recovery but also provide valuable information about mineralization and alteration (P. Weidelt 1982; J. Macnae 2016a; V. Kaminski & A. Viezzoli 2017). As outlined in Part A of this work, airborne IP research has historically emphasized helicopter-borne systems. Their fixed geometry and concentric-loop transmitter–receiver configurations provide a stable framework in which negative transients can be uniquely attributed to polarization effects (e.g. R.S. Smith & G.F. West 1988). This stability made helicopters the reference platform for early airborne IP (AIP) studies, ensuring both interpretability and repeatability in connecting measured responses to subsurface processes.

Fixed-wing systems, by contrast, present both challenges and opportunities. Their larger footprint, variable flight dynamics and different system geometries complicate the direct interpretation of IP responses from dataspace. However, their broader spatial coverage and acquisition efficiency make them suitable for regional-scale exploration (e.g. B.J. Minsley *et al.* 2021). In Part A of this work, it was demonstrated that the TEMPEST™ fixed-wing system is sensitive to IP effects, confirming its potential to record polarization responses at survey scale. Building on these results, this study extends the investigation to real survey data. The goal is to incorporate IP effects explicitly into fixed-wing AEM modelling and assess their geological significance. Specifically, we aim (i) to quantify and characterize IP responses in fixed-wing data sets, and (ii) to evaluate their implications for mineral exploration and regional mapping. Our analysis proceeds in two stages. First, we compare fixed-wing TEMPEST™ IP models with two overlapping SkyTEM³¹²FAST helicopter-borne lines from the Musgrave Province, South Australia. This provides a benchmark for consistency against the more established helicopter-based modelling routines. One of the SkyTEM lines includes negative transients, which serve as clear evidence of ground polarization and thus a critical test for the fixed-wing system. Secondly, we extend the fixed-wing modelling to the entire Musgrave Province survey conducted under the AusAEM project (A.Y. Ley Cooper *et al.* 2019). This regional application tests the feasibility of using fixed-wing systems to generate chargeability maps at exploration scale. The validity of these models is assessed against the known geology of the Nemo–Babel mineralization system (Z. Seat *et al.* 2007), providing a practical measure of their reliability.

Through this approach, we aim to demonstrate if fixed-wing systems, while more complex to interpret than helicopter platforms, can deliver meaningful IP information at both local and regional scales. This not only could broaden the applicability of airborne IP methodologies but could also highlight the potential of incorporating IP modelling into fixed-wing AEM surveys as a tool for large-scale mineral exploration and geological mapping.

MODELLING APPROACH

For this work all the forward responses and inversions have been computed using the *EEMverter* inversion scheme, a modelling tool proposed by G. Fiandaca *et al.* (2024) for electrical and electromagnetic data. This inversion scheme uses uncoupled meshes for the forward computation and the modelling mapping. The model parameters are defined on the nodes of one or more model meshes and are linked to the forward mesh discretization via interpolation. This approach has been also proposed by N.K. Christensen *et al.* (2017) for 1-D AEM, and by L.M. Madsen *et al.* (2020), B. Zhang *et al.* (2021) and K.W. Engerbretsen *et al.* (2022) for 3-D EM. For modelling, one forward mesh is defined for each data set in the acquisition location, and one or more model meshes are associated to the forward mesh to map the parameters. The model mesh can be spatially defined using 3-D voxels around the forward mesh (for which it is possible to set variable cell size and discretization) or as a 1-D model coincident with the forward mesh to perform a laterally constrained (LCI) style approach (E. Auken & A.V. Christensen 2004). The uncoupling of the forward and model mesh, as well as to allow the use of different model meshes for each parameter, also consents the application of different mesh geometries, discretization and regularization during inversion. The interpolation from the different model parameters \mathbf{M} on the nodes of each model mesh with the \mathbf{m}_i subdivision of the forward mesh is performed through matrix multiplication. Here the matrix \mathbf{F}_i holds the weights of the interpolation which depends on the distance between model mesh nodes and the subdivision \mathbf{i} -th of the forward mesh:

$$\mathbf{m}_i = \mathbf{f}_i(\mathbf{m}) = \mathbf{F}_i \cdot \mathbf{M}. \quad (1)$$

The forward computation is performed in frequency domain considering the receiver transfer function, filters, gating and transmitter waveform and then brought in time domain through fast Hankel transformation (as in F. Effersø *et al.* 1999), as indicated in part A of this work. The time-domain Jacobian for the \mathbf{i} -th forward mesh is computed as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{m}_i, \text{TD}} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{m}_i, \text{FD}}, \quad (2)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{T} holds the Hankel coefficients and the matrix \mathbf{A} implements the effects of the current waveform, time gate integration and filters. The frequency domain Jacobian $\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{m}_i, \text{FD}}$ is calculated in 1-D through finite difference using the adjoint method and the chain rule as in G. Fiandaca *et al.* (2013) and L.M. Madsen *et al.* (2020). To compute the model update in the Levenberg–Marquadt linearized approach inversion, the model-space Jacobian $\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{M}}$ is computed summing the contributions of all the forward meshes up, using the time domain decomposition with a forward mesh for each sounding (N.K. Christensen *et al.* 2017; L.M. Madsen *et al.* 2020; B. Zhang *et al.* 2021) as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{M}} = \sum_i \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{m}_i} \cdot \mathbf{F}_i^T \quad (3)$$

And the model update is:

$$\mathbf{M}_{n+1, j} = \mathbf{M}_{n, j} + \left[\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{M}, j}^T \mathbf{C}_d^{-1} \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{M}, i} + \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{R}, j}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_j + \lambda \mathbf{I} \right]^{-1} \cdot \left[\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{M}, j}^T \mathbf{C}_d^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{f}_{n, j}) + \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{R}, j}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_j \cdot \mathbf{M}_{n, j} \right], \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the regularization matrix, \mathbf{C}_d the covariance matrix on the data, $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{R}}$ the covariance matrix on the forward, λ

Figure 1. Location of coincident TEMPESTTM (black) and SkyTEM (blue) surveys over the geology of the Musgrave Province in South Australia.

the damping operator, \mathbf{d} the measured data and \mathbf{f}_n the not updated forward response. In this formalism, the subscript j indicates that the inversion process can be split in different cycles. In this formalism, the subscript j indicates that the inversion process can be split in different cycles. Each inversion cycle is an independent inversion which uses as starting model the final model of the previous inversion cycle. Each cycle can have different forward mesh (for instance changing the dimensionality of the forward response to 3-D after a first general 1-D inversion), parametrization (for instance to invert for the flight altitude after a first cycle where only the resistivity was modelled) and regularization. This solution allows us to make the inversion more versatile and user-controlled using one unique input file. After inversion, the depth of investigation (DOI) was estimated following the methodology proposed by G. Fiandaca *et al.* (2015).

For this study, the model space is parametrized through the Maximum Phase Angle Cole–Cole re-parametrization (G. Fiandaca *et al.* 2018), with the resulting parameters mapped across two distinct model meshes characterized by different geometrical configurations, as proposed by G. Fiandaca & A. Viezzoli (2021) and F. Dauti *et al.* (2023). Resistivity and phase are mapped onto a 2-D (X–Z) model mesh and are vertically and laterally regularized using relatively loose constraints (200–300 per cent lateral variation allowed). Given the limited spectral content of the AEM data (restricted to approximately two decades), the spectral parameters (τ_ϕ and C) are constrained to remain constant with depth while being free to vary laterally. This regularization strategy is designed to mitigate parameter correlations and enhance the sensitivity of chargeability with depth during inversion. For the purposes of this work, a 21-layer smooth model was employed for the SkyTEM inversion, incorporating both high-moment (HM) and low-moment (LM) Z component data, whereas a 15-layer smooth model was adopted for the TEMPESTTM X and Z components. This has been chosen as consequence of the TEMPESTTM smaller number of time windows

(15) and considering that we are inverting separately X and Z components. Reducing the number of layers reduces the number of inversion parameters and, as consequence, equivalences. Vertically, the model was discretized with an initial layer thickness of 4 m, increasing logarithmically to a maximum depth of 600 m, corresponding to the bottom of the last layer. The starting model was homogeneous, with resistivity fixed at 300 Ω m and chargeability at 10 mrad. Spectral parameters were initialized as laterally homogeneous, with τ_ϕ set to 0.001 s and C to 0.5. All inversions were performed with the same starting model (subject to differences in vertical discretization) and identical regularization settings to minimize model-driven bias. While the SkyTEM's HM and LM have been jointly modelled, the X and Z components of the TEMPESTTM system are modelled separately. This decision was taken to evaluate the differences in sensitivity of the two components to IP effects.

FIELD DATA ANALYSIS

In this section we consider results from the assessment of modelling TEMPESTTM field data including IP effects at various scales. First, we compare the modelling results between the TEMPESTTM system and the helicopter-borne SkyTEM system for two overlapping lines. This is done to verify the robustness and the comparability of the TEMPESTTM retrieved chargeability and resistivity models with the better-known helicopter airborne IP modelling. Then, a regional-scale airborne chargeability mapping has been attempted using a portion of the AusAEM TEMPESTTM data set. To conclude, to verify the accuracy of the regional scale modelling, a comparison of the retrieved results over a known mineralization is provided. All the three experiments have been done using data acquired in the Musgrave Province in South Australia.

Geologically, the Musgrave Province is an east–west elongated Mesoproterozoic orogenic belt with a width of some 50 and 500 km of strike length, bounded by younger continental basin

Figure 2. At top, (a), acquired data (black) and relative last iteration forward response (in yellow/gold) of inversion for both SkyTEM and TEMPESTTM systems (both X and Z component). For the SkyTEM only the High Moment is shown, given the larger presence of negative responses, but the inversion has been performed using both High Moment and Low Moment. In red the negative recordings are displayed for both systems. In (b), the retrieved resistivity (plot 1, 2 and 3 from top) and chargeability (plot 4, 5 and 6) models are displayed. At bottom of each section the continuous black line shows the inversion misfit computed for each sounding and its value is shown in the right axis.

(H.M. Howard *et al.* 2015). It includes a variety of high-grade amphibolite to granulite metamorphic grade basement rocks, intruded by granitic plutons, layered mafic to ultramafic intrusions of the Giles Complex and by mafic dykes. Outcrop is limited, primarily occurring as isolated hills and ranges. A significant part of the region is covered by a variably thick, complex and conductive regolith, including weathered basement, with an extensive transported overburden comprising alluvial, fluvial and aeolian deposits/sandplains (Fig. 8a). Areas of thicker cover are commonly associated with sediment-filled palaeovalleys filled with sands, silts and clays and calcretes. The province is traversed by a laterally extensive series of shear zone systems,

which impart a prominent east–west ‘grain’ to the country (R.B. Major & C.H.H. Connor 1993). Many of the pre-Pliocene palaeovalley systems, incised into the basement, exploit this structural grain. From an exploration standpoint, the Musgrave region is a prospective for magmatic nickel-copper, PGE’s, orogenic and intrusive gold, and iron oxide copper gold (IOCG) mineral systems. In this context, Airborne EM plays a crucial role in the exploration beneath a conductive cover, which can mask and/or distort the geophysical expression of a buried mineral system. From a simple modelling perspective, the geology of the Musgrave Province fits the two-layer model used in the synthetic

Figure 3. Example of data fit for a select group of (a) SkyTEM HM decays (b) TEMPEST™ Z and (c) X component transients. The SkyTEM data show a double change of sign (positive-negative-positive). The group of data are taken around 7.092×10^6 m Northing. The data is coloured (blue for positive voltages, red for negatives, grey for noisy) while the forward response is in black.

case study described in the previous section; specifically, an altered conductive regolith cover overlying a resistive basement. The synthetic modelling of Part A of this series on AIP in fixed-wing systems indicates that a shallow chargeable ground could be measured by the TEMPEST™ AEM system.

SkyTEM and TEMPEST™ AIP modelling comparison

For the first experiment two lines of TEMPEST™ HM (references in A.Y. Ley-Cooper 2017a, b) data are used. These were acquired in 2016 and are coincident with a SkyTEM³¹² Fast survey (T. Munday 2019 and T. Munday *et al.* 2023); the specifics of the two systems for this survey are listed in Table 1. The SkyTEM gate times are referred to a zero-time at the end of the ramp.

The study area with the location of the two surveys is shown in Fig. 1.

In the SkyTEM data set, the presence of a chargeable ground is indicated by strong negative voltages in the eastern line (as visible in the data stripe of Fig. 2a). As mentioned, the secondary field negative measurements are uniquely related to AIP effects when measured with a concentric-loop system (e.g. P. Weidelt 1982; R.S. Smith & G.F. West 1988). Even though the SkyTEM system is not a perfect concentric-loop system, it can be approximated as concentric-loop. The distance between the centre of transmitter loop and receiver coil is small enough (12.4 m) in comparison with the system's footprint (about 20–30 m in a conductive near surface) to avoid the recording of geometrical negative voltages.

Results from the modelling of the eastern-most line are shown in Figs 2(a) and (b). In Fig. 2(a), the measured data for both SkyTEM and TEMPEST™ are shown, in black, with its relative forward response retrieved after inversion (in yellow). An example of data-fit for a select group of decays from the SkyTEM system exhibiting a negative double-sign reversal is shown in Fig. 3. Culled gates, after manual processing, are shown in grey colour while the negative responses are shown in red. To assess the presence of IP effects, strong negative voltages have been recorded above the noise level in one SkyTEM line (Valen East). In the same location, weak negatives have been measured by the TEMPEST™ Z component, while strong sign reverse data are

recorded in the X component. This can be explained by the faster decay of the X component, permitting the detection of smaller AIP effects earlier. Also, given that the X component is normally positive in absence of geometrical effects, the IP effects appear more obvious as negative measurements (i.e. Fig. 2a, third panel from top).

Regarding the data fit, a generally good fit (below 2) has been retrieved after all the inversions. The misfit value is indicated by the continuous black line at bottom of each modelled section (Figs 2b and 3b) while the last-iteration forward response with the yellow/gold colour in the data stripe (Figs 2a and 3a). The data misfit is computed as in eq. (5).

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{d_{\text{obs}j} - \text{fwr}_j}{\text{std}_j} \right)^2}, \quad (5)$$

where d_{obs} indicates the measured data, fwr the forward response and std the uncertainty related to each time window; n indicates the number of gates while the index j indicates the gate for which the misfit is computed. The data uncertainty is expressed as percentage of the recorded data; for this data set, a uniform uncertainty of 5 per cent is set for each time window which is summed with the noise-level dependent uncertainty.

In Fig. 2(b), the model comparison is shown. The three resistivity models (SkyTEM combined high and low moment and TEMPEST™ Z and X components) are compared on the first three plots, while the chargeability models are shown in the lower panels. In all the sections, the faded portion masks the models below the DOI while the continuous black line (at the bottom of each section) represents the obtained data misfit; the misfit value is on the right axis of each section. The models for both systems show a conductive cover in the upper 100 m, overlying a more resistive bedrock hosting more conductive bodies (Fig. 2b). The more conductive near-surface responses are associated with palaeovalley fill materials which may contain brackish to saline groundwater. The chargeable domain, often uncoupled with the conductive domain in near surface, is stronger where the EM signal is weaker and where the negative voltages have been measured in the SkyTEM HM (with an example with a fitted double change of sign in Fig. 3) and in the TEMPEST™

Figure 4. In the top panels (a), the acquired data (black) and its relative last iteration forward response (in yellow/gold) for the inversion are shown for both heli-borne (SkyTEM) and fixed-wing AEM (TEMPESTTM) systems and for both the Z and X component of the TEMPESTTM AEM data set. For the SkyTEM only the High Moment is shown but the inversion has been performed using both High Moment and Low Moment. In (b), the retrieved resistivity (plot 1, 2 and 3 from top) and chargeability (plot 4, 5 and 6) models are displayed. The continuous black line shows the inversion misfit computed for each sounding and its value is shown in the right axis

X component. In the same location, a much smaller change of sign has been recorded in the Z component of the TEMPESTTM system but a chargeable domain, spatially coincident with the one modelled with the SkyTEM data, has been retrieved. For this line, the SkyTEM and TEMPESTTM chargeability models correspond very well in the resistive area of the model, between Easting 7.088×10^6 and 7.092×10^6 m. In the more conductive zones, SkyTEM and TEMPESTTM Z chargeability models show similar features in the near surface, where however the TEMPESTTM Z model exhibits more continuous and intense layering, often above the DOI. Conversely, the TEMPESTTM X chargeability model shows strong similarities with SkyTEM at greater depths (e.g. between Easting 7.092×10^6 and 7.094×10^6 m), again with anomalies more often above the DOI. It has to be highlighted

that the DOI computation in this study follows G. Fiandaca *et al.* (2015), where also the correlation between the Cole and Cole parameters contributes to the DOI calculation. Following this approach, anomalies that have a considerable effect on the data can result under the DOI when they are correlated with anomalies at the same depth of other parameters. In this sense, the TEMPESTTM X component gives a more data-driven anomaly which, in this specific case, results above the depth of investigation.

The negative data content for the two systems conforms with the synthetic modelling results of part A of this work series. Specifically, where the ground is more resistive, pure EM currents are weaker, and IP effects are stronger. This is reflected both in the SkyTEM data and in the TEMPESTTM data, more in

Figure 5. AIP and non-AIP models for the Musgrave Province at 50 m depth. The models are retrieved from the TEMPEST™ Z component inversion. In (a) the surface lithology is shown. In (b), the resistivity model retrieved not considering AIP is mapped. In (c) the chargeability model for the area is shown while in (d) the resistivity retrieved for the AIP inversion. In (e), the percentage difference computed as in eq. (6) is shown for this depth slice. The red dot indicates the location of the Nebo-Babel mineralization, object of the deposit-scale experiment.

Figure 6. Resistivity (a) and chargeability (c) models retrieved for a depth slice at 130 m. The non-AIP inversion result is shown in fig. (b). In (d), the percentage difference between the resistivity models is visible. The red dot represents the location of the Nebo-Babel deposit.

the X component than in the Z. Although differences in the negative recordings content, a spatially coherent chargeable near-surface domain has been retrieved in the models for both systems. This behaviour is consistent with the known distribution of regolith materials in the area as discussed by T. Munday *et al.* (2020a,b, and 2023). The chargeability–regolith coupling has been confirmed by drilling and has been attributed in large part to the distribution of magnetite and maghemite in the landscape following weathering and transport. R. R. Anand and M. Paine (2002) have noted that resistant very fine-grained magnetite and secondary maghemite, concentrated by landscape processes within the regolith, are common across Australia. When maghemite is developed, it can display a variable remanence, susceptibility, chargeability and superparamagnetic behaviour (D. Clark & D. Emerson 1991; D.A. Clark 1997). In regolith-dominated terrains, such as found in the study area, fine grained magnetic materials occur throughout the regolith and are often found concentrated in lenses or layers within transported materials (J. Macnae *et al.* 2020). This chargeability distribution is apparent in the second line flown (Fig. 4) in the Valen West survey area (Fig. 1). In contrast to the line from the eastern study area, no negative data have been recorded for either the SkyTEM or TEMPEST™ systems (see Fig. 4a). However, a chargeable domain coupled with the conductive cover has been modelled in all the inversions (see Fig. 4b). Similar resistivity and chargeability models are recovered for data from both systems, with the regolith exhibiting the most conductive and chargeable responses. In contrast to modelled chargeability results for the eastern-most line (Fig. 2), which suggested a chargeable near surface layer over an area of subcrop/outcrop

in the centre of the line, the western-most line (Fig. 4), a similar area of subcrop (centre of the line) does not return a chargeable response. We attribute this to a change in the basement geology present.

In summary, a good correlation is noted between the TEMPEST™ and SkyTEM³¹² modelled chargeability and resistivity/conductivity responses, supporting the assertion that AIP can be successfully modelled also from fixed-wing AEM systems such as the TEMPEST™ system consistently with helicopter-borne systems.

Regional scale field data modelling

Following the comparative study between AIP, we undertook a more detailed examination of a larger TEMPEST™ data set covering the western Musgrave Province, in South Australia and acquired as part of the AusAEM project. These data were acquired using the standard TEMPEST™ system for an amount of 20k line km of data flown with a line spacing of ~2 km (A.Y. Ley Cooper *et al.* 2019). The data have been pre-processed using a slope-based filters to remove the noisy gates and then manually refined removing the remaining outliers. The entire data set has been modelled using the same approach as described for the initial study on individual lines, both considering and neglecting IP effects. For this modelling test, only the Z component of the TEMPEST™ has been used. This choice has been made after an evaluation about the better S/N for this component in the region. Although in very conductive areas both the Z component and X component can be above noise level, when the cover is thinner and the resistive outcrop is closer to surface the X component

Figure 7. Non-AIP retrieved resistivity (a), AIP retrieved resistivity (b) and percentage difference between the two (c).

gets noisier and the data are poorly informative of the subsurface. Moreover, given the horizontal component sensitivity to pitch variations, we assumed it safer (to prove the AIP modelling reliability) to attempt the regional-scale modelling on the Z component only. The results of the modelling are shown in Fig. 5. In this figure, derived models are overlain on the surface geology for the area shown in Fig. 5(a). A gridded resistivity-depth interval (50 m below the ground surface) modelled from data without considering AIP is shown in Fig. 5(b); results from inverting the data including IP are presented in Fig. 5(c) (chargeability) and Fig. 5(d) (resistivity) for the same depth interval. Examination of the modelled resistivities show how the more conductive parts of the landscape are associated with mapped areas of cover. The most chargeable areas (Fig. 5c) appear to be confined to mapped areas of outcrop/subcrop where weathering/erosion is likely to have left a thin regolith.

In Fig. 5(e) the percentage difference between the IP and non-IP retrieved resistivities is shown. The difference is computed as in eq. (6):

$$\text{Percentage Difference}_j = \left| \frac{\rho_{\text{noIP}j} - \rho_{\text{IP}j}}{\rho_{\text{noIP}j}} \right|, \quad (6)$$

where ρ_{IP} and ρ_{noIP} represents, respectively, the dispersive and non-dispersive resistivity value of the j -th layer of the model.

Although the apparent similarities between the two resistivity models of Figs 5(b) and (d), their percentage difference (Figs 5e) highlights significant discrepancies that easily reach 100 per cent. The area with the most difference mirrors the subsurface chargeability distribution. This is also coincident with areas of outcropping geology (see Fig. 5a). As seen from synthetics of Part A of this work, as the cover conductance increases, the purely EM currents dominate the polarization currents making the ground chargeability effects weak in the AEM data. This explains the consistent chargeability model with the outcropping geology and its uncoupling with high-conductivity regions.

A similar behaviour is noted for models at greater depth. These are shown in Fig. 6, with resistivity (Fig. 6b for non-AIP modelling and Fig. 6d including IP) and chargeability (Fig. 6c) slices at 130 m below ground surface. The percentage difference between dispersive and non-dispersive resistivity models is shown in Fig. 6(d).

An increase in the depth results in an increase in the extent of the resistive domain, while the chargeability reduces. The differences between the resistivity models (Fig. 6d) also increases, with the AIP retrieved resistivity showing greater variability at this depth in comparison with the non-AIP one. This is attributed to the AIP modelling, where the fast decays given by the ground polarization are fitted using IP parameters rather than increasing ground resistivity. Follows that, at this depth, the percentage difference often exceeds the 100 per cent and, in general, its values tend to increase with depth.

To highlight the differences between the AIP and non-IP retrieved resistivity models, the distribution of resistivities modelled at all the depths are shown in Fig. 7. A percentage difference of the two (Figs 7a and b), computed as in eq. (6), is also shown in Fig. 7(c).

The main differences between the two resistivity distributions are at high resistivities, where the IP modelling fits the fast decays/negatives with IP parameters instead of only increasing the ground resistivity. This explains the higher number of high-resistivities for the non-IP modelling. The differences between the models span from few per cent and reach a peak value at 100 per cent for about 7×10^4 cases.

In Fig. 8(a) comparison of model misfits is shown, for non-AIP inversion (Fig. 8a) and AIP inversion (Fig. 8b). The results suggest that modelling the TEMPEST™ data using AIP increases the reliability of the retrieved models improving the data-fit, as indicated by the significant reduction of inversion misfit of Fig. 8. It is also interesting to note how the misfit distribution in non-AIP modelling follows the chargeability distribution of Figs 5(c) and 6(c), suggesting a data-driven chargeability modelling.

Deposit scale analysis

In this final section, we compare the TEMPEST™ resistivity and chargeability models with the geological model of a known mineralization (Fig. 9, Fig. 10), the Nebo-Babel deposit (Z. Seat *et al.* 2007; B. Godel *et al.* 2011; B.A. Grguric *et al.* 2018). This deposit is a Ni-Cu-platinum-element (PGE) sulphide deposit hosted in a gabbro-norite intrusion and offset by the Jameson Fault that splits it two main bodies, the Nebo and Babel. The mineralization occurs as a massive sulphide breccias and as disseminated gabbro-norite-hosted sulphides (Z. Seat *et al.* 2007). Z. Seat *et al.* (2009), noted that massive sulphide occurs as lenses of <3 m

Figure 8. Misfit comparisons for the non-AIP (a) and AIP inversion (b). A clear misfit reduction is visible when AIP is considered during modelling.

Table 1. AEM system specifications for coincident surveys of SkyTEM and TEMPEST™ data in the Musgrave province of South Australia.

AEM System parameters	TEMPEST High moment	SkyTEM ³¹² FAST
Tx Diameter (m)	26	28.6–30.6
No. Turns	1	2 (LM) 12 (HM)
Tx Area (m ²)	244	342
Tx Elevation (m)	120	45–60
Nominal Current (A)	1200	5.77 (LM) 109.9 (HM)
Peak Moment (A m ²)	292 800	3946 (LM) 451029.6 (HM)
Base frequency (Hz)	25	25
Rx Elevation (m)	50	45–60
Waveform	Square	Pseudo-rectangular
Duty Cycle	50 per cent	44 per cent (LM) 25 per cent (HM)
Gate Centre (ms) (for TEMPEST™ after conversion to square-wave magnetic B field)	0.013–16.2	16.41 μs to 0.861 ms (LM) 436.41 μs to 13.18 (HM)
No. Channels/Gates	15	18 (LM); 17 (HM)

thickness, in the Babel deposit, in contact with the orthogneiss wall rocks. The mineralogy of the ore deposit consists mainly of pyrrhotite, pentlandite, chalcopyrite and trace pyrite both for the massive portion and for the disseminated part. The main host unit of the disseminated sulphides is the fine-grained mineralized gabbronorite, the mineralized gabbronorite and the leucogabbronorite. The disseminated portion of the deposit is geometrically defined in the upper hanging-wall contact with the country rocks adjacent to the mineralized gabbronorite hosting the massive sulphides (Z. Seat *et al.* 2009). In geophysical terms, the massive sulphide body should give a conductivity contrast while the disseminated sulphide portions a chargeability contrast.

The Nebo-Babel mineralization is overlapped by a portion of one line (L3608001) of the AusAEM TEMPEST™ survey, as shown in red in Fig. 9. The orebodies were defined after an extensive drilling campaign. A geological section for the Babel mineral system is shown in Fig. 10, corresponding to the dashed line shown on the map on the lower-left side.

The geological section across the Babel deposit (by Z. Seat *et al.* 2009), derived from borehole information and geological reasoning (Z. Seat *et al.* 2007; Z. Seat *et al.* 2009), has been modified by

the authors to highlight the portions of the orebody with different mineralization styles. The red outline encloses the disseminated portion of the deposit; this is hosted in the variably textured leucogabbro and in the mineralized gabbronorite on the upper hanging wall with the country rocks (the disseminated part corresponding to the VLGN lithology). The black outline describes the deeper portion of the deposit, hosted in the mineralized/fine grained gabbronorite.

The TEMPEST™ models for the Babel deposit are presented in Fig. 11.

The retrieved conductivity and chargeability models are consistent with the geological interpretation presented in Fig. 10. A chargeable body (in the red outline, located at easting 3.7×10^5 m) is encapsulated in a strongly conductive body (in grey, in Fig. 10). As presented in the literature (Z. Seat *et al.* 2007, 2009) and supported by the drillholes, the near surface domain is characterized by a lower conductivity and chargeable zone—associated with the disseminated domain of the orebody—while at depth the mineralization gets massive and gives a conductive anomaly (Fig. 11). The retrieved model mapped the known mineralization and described it not only in terms of conductivity (that constitutes the main electrical feature of this mineral body)

Figure 9. AusAEM TEMPEST™ portion of line 3 608 001 (in red) over the surface projection of the Nebo-Babel orebodies. The geological legend abbreviations indicate: barren gabbronorite (BGN), fine-grained mineralized gabbronorite (F.G. MGN), gabbronorite (GN), mineralized gabbronorite (MGN) and variably textured leuco-gabbronorite (VLGN). The black dashed lines in the map show the location of the geological cross section. Modified from Z. Seat *et al.* (2009).

Figure 10. Babel geological cross-section modified from Z. Seat *et al.* (2009) with locations of drillholes. The geological legend is the same as that described in Fig. 16. The red outline has been added by the authors to highlight the disseminated mineralization domain while the black outline defines the main conductive orebody. Equal vertical/horizontal scales are used in the section.

but also in terms of chargeability. A 3-D visualization of geophysical and geological models is shown in Fig. 12, also showing the geometrical relationship between the geological cross-section and the TEMPEST™ flight line. In Fig. 12(a) the geological model of Fig. 10 is shown; in Figs 12(c) and (d) the resistivity and chargeability models are shown, respectively, while in

Fig. 12(b) the integration of the three models is represented. In Fig. 12(b) only the outline of the chargeable portion is outlined (in black) to highlight its relationship with the conductive body in background.

This final experiment in this study confirms the sensitivity of the TEMPEST™ AEM fixed-wing system to chargeable and

Figure 11. Modelling results for the TEMPEST™ line overlapping the Babel deposit. Two outlines, derived from the geophysical results, are represented: the red outline marks the chargeable body while the grey line defines the larger conductive body. The aspect ratio of the figure is 1:1, as for the geological model. Overall, there is a good correspondence between the geometries retrieved by AIP and the geological model, even if in the latter the MGN formation extends to greater depths.

Figure 12. 3-D views of the geological (a), resistivity (c) and chargeability (d) models, together with a combined visualization of the three models (b). In (b), only the outline of the highly chargeable (>30 mrad in yellow, >50 mrad in brown) zone associated with disseminated mineralization is displayed, superimposed on the resistivity model and compared to the geological section.

conductive mineral targets, demonstrating the potential of the TEMPEST™-derived chargeability model as an interpretation tool for narrowing the exploration process from regional to deposit scale.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the capability of recovering ground chargeability from airborne EM fixed-wing TEMPEST™ data.

Resistivity and chargeability models derived from TEMPEST™ AIP inversions were directly compared with SkyTEM AIP models along two survey lines, both in the presence and absence of negative measurements in the helicopter-borne data. The comparison showed a good consistency, both for the TEMPEST™ Z and X component inversions. Beyond geophysical comparability between different airborne systems, geological coherence between the TEMPEST™-derived chargeability and resistivity models and the mapped lithology of the Musgrave Province (South Australia, 20 000 line-km of data) was also observed. At regional scale, the comparison between AIP and non-AIP inversions of the Musgrave models shown high differences, often higher than 100 per cent, between the retrieved resistivity models. Also, non-AIP inversions consistently yielded higher inversion misfits over large portions of the study area when compared with dispersive resistivity models, particularly in correspondence of chargeable regions. The scalability of incorporating IP effects in fixed-wing AEM inversion was further confirmed in a detailed case study over the Nebo–Babel mineralization. Here, the airborne-derived chargeability response of Musgrave-region was spatially correlated with disseminated mineralization in the near-surface portion of the Babel orebody, while the deeper massive sulphide mineralization was expressed as a distinct conductivity anomaly. These results highlight both the regional and deposit-scale potential of fixed-wing AEM systems for chargeability mapping and demonstrate their capability to provide geologically meaningful information that complements conventional resistivity imaging.

We believe that Part A and Part B of this study help bridge the gap in understanding and extracting IP effects between helicopter-based and fixed-wing aircraft systems, demonstrating comparable sensitivity to polarization. Furthermore, the regional and continental-scale analysis of TEMPEST™ data has allowed IP effects to be correlated with geology at an unprecedented scale, paving the way for a deeper understanding and applicability of AEM IP effects.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The AusAEM data used for the regional modelling are publicly available from the Geoscience Australia portal (<https://www.eftf.ga.gov.au/ausaem>). The Musgrave SkyTEM and TEMPEST™

High Moment data discussed in this paper are publicly available and can be obtained directly from Tim Munday, CSIRO (tim.munday@csiro.au).

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